

ISic0824

I.Sicily inscription 0824

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Theatre of Hieron, Siracusa

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [βασιλέως Γέλωνος]

1. βασίλισσας Νηρηΐδος

1. βασίλισσας Φιλιστίδος

1. [β]ασιλ[έως Ίέρω]νος

1. Διὸς Ὀλυμπίου

0. [---]

1. [Ἡρ]ακλέος [Κ]ρατε[ρό]φρονο[ς]

0. [---]

0. [---]

Apparatus

Text based on Dimartino 2017

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285055

EDR 114400

EDCS 39101972

PHI 140292

PHI 332314

Bibliography

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